

The impact of global warming on UK convenience stores and their challenges and opportunities to adapt

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ABSTRACT

As global temperatures rise due to climate change, convenience stores face increasing challenges in maintaining optimal refrigeration and store temperatures. This study evaluates the impact of extreme heat on a small independent UK convenience store using an EnergyPlus™ model to simulate thermal dynamics during the UK July 2022 heatwave. The analysis examines air conditioning (A/C) performance, refrigeration efficiency, and indoor temperature stability under varying cooling capacities. Results show that if the A/C system was designed using EnergyPlus™ algorithms, there would be sufficient spare capacity, with the model predicting that the store temperature would stay stable even during outdoor peaks of 40.15°C. Sizing for a peak outdoor temperature of 27.7°C revealed that indoor temperatures exceeded the setpoint by 4.0°C. To enhance store resilience, strategies such as A/C sizing for higher peak temperatures are advised to adapt for future climate conditions.

Keywords: Climate change, Convenience stores, EnergyPlus™, Refrigeration, HVAC, Heatwave

1 INTRODUCTION

In December 2015, the UK, along with 195 other countries, signed the Paris Agreement (UNFCCC, 2016), a global commitment to cutting greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and reducing the worst impact of climate change. However, even with these efforts, some changes to the climate are already unavoidable because of past emissions. This means that we need to evaluate the weaknesses and vulnerabilities of systems and their ability to cope with climatic changes (Schneider et al., 2007). As climate change becomes inevitable, we need to enhance the resilience of society while at the same time protecting the environment (HM Government, 2017).

According to the UK Met office predictions (Met Office, 2025), due to climate changes across the UK, it is projected that summers will become 1 to 6°C warmer and up to 60% drier by 2070 compared to 1990. Winters are projected to be warmer by 1 to 4.5°C. It is therefore essential that the impact of these changes on all businesses be studied to ensure there is a plan for facing these risks (DEFRA, 2024).

The food supply chain is one of the 13 sectors classified as Critical National Infrastructure by the UK government (Cabinet Office, 2017) that will be affected by temperature changes considerably. In 2019, the Environmental Audit Committee of the UK House of Commons expressed its concern about the vulnerabilities of this sector (UK Parliament, 2019). Studies indicate that the UK's leading food retailers have already recognised the importance of climate change and its impact on their business (Jones & Comfort, 2019). The largest retailers, with the majority of the market, have also taken some steps to enhance their resilience against changes in climate by focusing on supply chain security, reducing carbon emissions by investment in energy efficient refrigeration systems, as well as supporting farmers (Jones & Comfort, 2019).

While large supermarket chains have been the focus of most energy and environmental research, convenience stores have largely been overlooked. There is little reliable information on how prepared these smaller stores are for climate change. However, this sector has been growing in scale especially after the COVID-19 pandemic, in response to evolving societal needs. The number of convenience stores has increased from 46,262 stores in 2018 to more than 50,000 stores in 2024, with 71% of them operating independently (ACS, 2018, 2024). Smaller stores, such as independent convenience stores, usually have a higher ratio of

food products compared to non-food items (Franco et al., 2021). Since many food products require refrigeration, these stores tend to have a higher density of refrigerated display cabinets (Galvez-Martos et al., 2013). Therefore, refrigeration systems are a major user of energy in convenience stores. According to the Association of Convenience Stores (ACS), the share of investment in refrigeration system in convenience stores has increased from 32% out of £534m in 2021 to 56% of over £1b of total investment in 2024 (ACS, 2021, 2024). It also needs to be considered that small stores often rely on integral refrigeration systems, which can be less efficient, compared to remote refrigeration system in supermarkets (Tassou et al., 2011).

This background highlights a clear gap in understanding in this growing sub-sector of the food supply chain and emphasises the urgent need for focused research on the adaptation challenges faces by independent convenience stores. This study investigates the impact of climate change on a selected archetype of convenience stores in the UK by developing an EnergyPlus™ building energy model (U.S. Department of Energy, 2024a). It simulates the thermal dynamics of the store and evaluates the effects of the extreme heatwave of the summer of 2022 in the UK. The aim was to analyse how the store temperature and refrigeration system responded under these conditions, and to assess the performance of the air conditioning (A/C) system.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Information on convenience stores

Independent convenience stores tend to have smaller sales areas compared to larger chain-operated stores (ACS, 2024). As shown in Figure 1, most of these independent stores (91%) are operating in less than 186 m² (1,999 ft²) sales area. These represent about 32,555 stores in the UK. In contrast, larger retailers which are operating ten or more convenience stores (multiples), dominate larger store formats, particularly in the 186–280 m² (2,000–3,000 ft²) range of sales area. Independent convenience stores with an area of less than 186 m² (1,999 ft²) were the focus of this study.

To better understand the design of refrigeration systems in this group of independent stores, ten London independent convenience stores were visited. During these visits, the number of cabinets, and their length was estimated and reported (Table 1). The average total length of both low temperature (LT) and medium temperature (MT) cabinets were estimated. Data on the primary energy source for heating were collected from the store energy performance certificate (EPC) and it was checked whether they had A/C systems. Findings indicated that all these stores were using electricity for heating and only one of them was equipped with an A/C system in the store. All the cabinets were equipped with integrated refrigeration systems, with the majority consisting of open vertical chilled cabinets and chest freezers, as shown in Table 2.

Figure 1. Sales area of UK convenience stores

Table 1. Collected data for stores

No.	Sales area (m ²)	Cabinet MT length (m)	Cabinet LT length (m)	A/C
1	28.78	3	0	No
2	52.5	10.5	5	No
3	81.3	8.25	2	No
4	91.05	10.10	4.2	No
5	59.99	4.55	0	No
6	70.4	11	1.25	Yes
7	19.34	2.4	0	No
8	85.8	11.4	4.85	No
9	100.4	9.37	3.87	No
10	40.5	7.2	7	No
Average	63.0	7.77	2.82	

Table 2. Refrigeration equipment specification in stores

No.	Length of refrigerator (m)			Length of freezer (m)		
	Cabinets without doors	Cabinets with doors	Beverage (with doors)	Vertical freezer	Ice cream chest freezer	Ice cream display freezer
1	3	0	0	0	0	0
2	10.5	0	0	0	5	0
3	4.5	3.75	0	0	2	0
4	9.6	0	0.5	1.2	3	0
5	3.3	1.25	0	0	0	0
6	11	0	0	1.25	0	0
7	2.4	0	0	0	0	0
8	9.9	1.5	0	3.75	0	1.1
9	7.5	1.875	0	1.9	2	0
10	7.2	0	0	0	6	1

2.2 Modelling of the convenience store

2.2.1 Methodology

Five software programs were used: EnergyPlus™ v24.2.0 (U.S. Department of Energy, 2024a), OpenStudio® v.1.8.0 (U.S. Department of Energy, 2024b), Elements v1.0.6 (Big Ladder Software, 2024), Coolselector®2 v.5.5.2 (Danfoss, 2025) and DView v1.2 (NREL, 2024). The model geometry was created using FloorspaceJS, an open-source tool within OpenStudio® (the graphical interface of EnergyPlus™). OpenStudio® was used to integrate various model parameters, such as weather files, construction materials, occupancy, internal loads, schedules, HVAC, and refrigeration systems. The Elements tool, a weather data processing application, was used to replicate the heatwave conditions of 19 July 2022. Coolselector®2 was used for selecting condensing units and obtaining compressor data. EnergyPlus™, the primary engine for building energy simulations, was used to perform the simulations. DView, the data visualisation tool for EnergyPlus™, was employed to analyse the simulation output data of EnergyPlus™ to assess the impact of the heatwave on the store.

2.2.2 Geometry

A 63 m² sales area store was modelled as this represented the average of all the independent stores visited.

The store was assumed to be square, and the height was 3 m based on BibLus (2024), who state the required height for newly constructed premises must be at least 3 m. The store's door size was 2 m x 1.5 m (height x width).

2.2.3 Model inputs

Full detailed information on the model inputs are provided in Table 3.

The historical London EnergyPlus weather files, including a design day (DDY) file, were based on average data from 1976-2005 and obtained from the EnergyPlus website. These files were initially used to represent typical building design conditions.

To define the envelope of the store, a recent standard construction set from the American Society of Heating, Refrigeration and Air Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE) within the library was employed (90.1-2019 – ASHRAE 169-2013), using materials from OpenStudio's built-in libraries.

OpenStudio encompassed various parameters such as the store operational hours, occupancy, lighting, equipment usage, and specific operation times for various components. All electrical devices were added in OpenStudio as electrical input loads. EnergyPlus ASHRAE defaults (90.1-2019 – ASHRAE 169-2013) were used for lighting and electrical loads.

By default, the HVAC system and inputs such as flow rates, heating and cooling capacities were "auto sized" by EnergyPlus using sizing algorithms. These were derived from heating and cooling loads at design conditions from the weather files. The HVAC aimed to control the sales area via a thermostat set point. The sales area was serviced by a packaged rooftop unit (PRU) equipped with a direct expansion (DX) cooling coil, electrical resistive heating coil, supply fan, and an outside air system on the supply side. Even though only one store had A/C, this study considers a store with A/C to assess the performance of the A/C system under various scenarios. The A/C coefficient of performance ($COP_{A/C}$) was calculated based on the outdoor dry bulb temperatures (T_{out}) and wet-bulb temperatures (T_w) using a biquadratic equation with default coefficients in EnergyPlus:

$$COP_{A/C} = \frac{COP_{R,A/C}}{0.3424 + 3.488e^{-2} T_{out} - 6.237e^{-4} T_w^2 + 4.977e^{-3} T_{out} + 4.379e^{-4} T_{out}^2 - 7.280e^{-4} T_w T_{out}} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

where $COP_{A/C}$ is the COP at different temperatures and $COP_{R,A/C}$ is at rated conditions, based on standardised testing environments by industry practices applied by EnergyPlus (air entering the cooling coil at a T_w of 19.4°C and air entering the outdoor condenser coil at a T_{out} of 35°C). An economiser (uses outdoor air if T_{out} is below the setpoint) was integrated into the HVAC system to provide free cooling from outside when the external air conditions were favourable, instead of relying on mechanical cooling.

The refrigeration system consisted entirely of integral units, with a closed frozen cabinet (chest freezer) and open chilled vertical cabinets. These integral units were equipped with fixed speed condenser fans. The COP of the chilled refrigeration system ($COP_{r,c}$) and the COP of the frozen refrigeration system ($COP_{r,f}$) were determined using two quadratic curves influenced by indoor temperature (T_{in}). These curves were derived from data on two condensing units selected from Coolselector2: the Optyma Slim Pack OP-MSXM044MLW09G with compressor model MLZ019T5 for the chilled system, and the Optyma OP-LCQN068NTA02G with compressor model NTZ068-5B for the frozen system:

$$COP_{r,c} = 0.001141T_{in}^2 - 0.1486T_{in} + 5.6114 \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

$$COP_{r,f} = 0.000135T_{in}^2 - 0.0355T_{in} + 1.9559 \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

Based on these COP values, the compressor electrical power for the chilled refrigeration system ($P_{r,c}$) and the frozen refrigeration system ($P_{r,f}$) were calculated using the chilled refrigeration system heat extraction ($Q_{r,c}$), and frozen refrigeration system heat extraction ($Q_{r,f}$), as follows:

$$P_{r,c} = \frac{Q_{r,c}}{COP_{r,c}} \quad \text{Eq. (4)}$$

$$P_{r,f} = \frac{Q_{r,f}}{COP_{r,f}} \quad \text{Eq. (5)}$$

Table 3. Model inputs

PARAMETERS	INPUTS		SOURCE	
Opening hours (OH)	From 7 am – 10 pm (Monday-Sunday)		ACS (2021)	
HVAC system	Heating thermostat (°C)	18 (OH) and 16 (CH)		Assumption
	Cooling thermostat (°C)	24		Eid et al. (2024)
	$COP_{R,A/C}$	3		Goel et al. (2017)
	Heating efficiency	1		EnergyPlus default
	Fan total efficiency	0.7		EnergyPlus default
	Motor efficiency	0.9		EnergyPlus default
	Fan pressure rise (Pa)	500		EnergyPlus default
	Heating design supply T (°C)	40		EnergyPlus default
	Cooling design supply T (°C)	15		EnergyPlus default
	Economiser limit T_{out} (°C)	21		IECC (2012)
Refrigeration system		Chilled	Frozen	
	Case length (m)	7.77	2.82	Table 1
	Operating T (°C)	4	-20	Assumption
	Evaporating T (°C)	-7	-30	Assumption
	Cooling capacity (W/m)	1547	675	Expert advice
	Evaporator fan power (W/m)	12	0	Smeta (2025) Assumption
	Condenser fan power (W/m)	19.2	7.2	Smeta (2025) Assumption
	Case lighting power (W/m)	20 (OH) 5 (CH)	20 (OH) 5 (CH)	Eid et al. (2024) Assumption
	Case height (m)	1.5	1.5	EnergyPlus default
	Case infiltration percentage ¹ (%)	100	5 (OH) 2.5 (CH)	Assumption
	Latent heat ratio	0.3	0.1	EnergyPlus default

2.3 Heatwave weather data

According to the UK Met Office (2023), the summer of 2022 saw the highest recorded temperature in Coningsby, UK, reaching 40.3°C on 19 July 2022, which led to the issuance of the first-ever Level 4 Heat-Health Alert (HHA). To examine the impact of this specific heatwave on the store, the conditions from that day, as reported by Weatherspark (2024), were replicated and integrated into the historical EnergyPlus weather file using the Elements tool. This involved modifying the conditions for that day, including T_{out} , wet-bulb temperatures, dew point temperatures, relative humidity, and wind speeds, using data from the Coningsby Royal Air Force base. This adjustment aimed to ensure an accurate representation of the heatwave event on that day in the UK. Figure 2 shows T_{out} during the heatwave on 19 July, 2022, at Coningsby Royal Air Force base, UK.

¹ 100% represents a fully open case with maximum infiltration, while 0% indicates a closed case with no infiltration. Values in between indicate partial infiltration, resulting from people opening and closing the cabinet doors.

Figure 2. T_{out} during the heatwave at Coningsby Royal Air Force base, UK

2.4 A/C system auto-sizing using historical EnergyPlus weather files

The A/C system was sized using EnergyPlus' auto-design capabilities, based on the historical weather files for London and the corresponding DDY file. The goal was to determine the auto-sized capacity under design conditions, evaluate whether any unmet hours occurred in the simulations (defined as periods when T_{in} fall outside the specified heating or cooling setpoints due to the HVAC system's inability to maintain thermal conditions), and verify that the system operated within the designated dual setpoints.

2.5 Assessment of heatwave impact on store temperature

To evaluate the impact of extreme weather conditions on T_{in} , the heatwave that occurred on July 19, 2022, was modelled. The aim was to explore the differences in A/C performance when applying a sizing factor of 1.15, as recommended by ASHRAE guidelines (ASHRAE Standard 90.1), compared to simulations without a sizing factor. Both manually-sized and auto-sized cooling capacities were analysed to assess their effect on maintaining store temperature within the specified setpoints.

2.6 Assessment of heatwave impact on refrigeration

The evaluation of the impact of extreme weather conditions on refrigeration performance was modelled in a similar manner to the A/C system analysis. The aim was to explore the differences in refrigeration system performance, including COPs.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 A/C maximum rated design

Using the historical EnergyPlus weather files for London alongside the corresponding design file in DDY format, where the maximum design T_{out} was 27.7°C, the EnergyPlus auto-size determined that the cooling coil capacity at design conditions was 10,632 W when applying a sizing factor of 1.15. The store temperature was successfully maintained within the range of 16°C to 24°C (upper and lower dual setpoints of the HVAC) throughout the year, with no unmet hours recorded.

3.2 Impact of the heatwave on the store temperature

The impact of the heatwave of 19 July 2022 on the store temperature under a number of different A/C design conditions are shown below.

3.2.1 Auto-sized cooling coil

Figure 3 shows T_{out} , T_{in} , A/C heat extraction ($Q_{A/C}$), and the A/C compressor electrical power ($P_{A/C}$) for the selected heatwave day using an A/C sizing factor of 1.15. This graph shows that T_{in} remained steady at 24°C, indicating that the A/C system could effectively handling the significant rise in T_{out} , which peaked at 40.15°C at 15:00. The $Q_{A/C}$ reached a maximum of 6,293 W and a $P_{A/C}$ a maximum of 2,538 W. Between 03:00 and 06:00, $Q_{A/C}$ and $P_{A/C}$ drop significantly approaching near zero. This occurs because T_{out} falls below 21°C, which was the set point of the economiser. As a result, the economiser activated, allowing fresh outside air to be introduced instead of relying on mechanical cooling. Figure 4 shows the $COP_{A/C}$ which is influenced by T_{out} , and the lowest $COP_{A/C}$ is recorded during the peak T_{out} at 2.47.

Figure 3. T_{out} , T_{in} , $Q_{A/C}$ and $P_{A/C}$ with a sizing factor of 1.15 – auto-sized

Figure 4. $COP_{A/C}$ with a sizing factor of 1.15 – auto-sized

As the design was able to meet the cooling demands during the heatwave, an additional simulation was carried out without this sizing factor. Figure 5 illustrates T_{out} , T_{in} , $Q_{A/C}$ and $P_{A/C}$ without a sizing factor. T_{in} also remained steady at 24°C, demonstrating that the A/C system was still successfully managing the substantial increase in T_{out} .

Figure 5. T_{out}, T_{in}, Q_{A/C} and P_{A/C} without a sizing factor – auto-sized

These results indicate that EnergyPlus oversizes the cooling coil capacity for this scenario. To address this issue and examine the impact of the heatwave on equipment originally sized under normal conditions (based on the same DDY file), the cooling coil capacity was manually-sized to determine the threshold at which the system could no longer meet the cooling demand as shown in section 3.2.2.

3.2.2 Manual-sized cooling coil

Through iterative testing on the historical EnergyPlus weather file, the threshold at which the system could no longer cope was identified as 6,470 W. A capacity below 6,470 W caused T_{in} to exceed the cooling setpoint of 24°C, indicating that the system was unable to handle the T_{out} increase effectively. Therefore, this subsection presents simulations illustrating the heatwave's impact on system performance, with manual-sizing approaches based on sizing factors of 1 (6,470 W) and 1.15 (7,440 W).

Starting with a manual-sizing factor of 1.15 (Figure 6), it appeared that the system began to struggle, with the T_{in} exceeding the setpoint by a maximum of 0.3°C at 15:00. The graph also shows that Q_{A/C} began to decline near the peak T_{out} and was unable to manage the rising temperature effectively, due to the reduced COP_{A/C}. Although these changes were minor, they indicate that the system was starting to have difficulty maintaining the original design conditions under the heatwave scenario. The temperature exceeded the cooling setpoint from 14:00 to 17:00.

Figure 7 illustrates the simulation without the sizing factor and shows a more significant increase in store temperature, exceeding the setpoint by a maximum of 4.0°C at 17:00. As in the previous test, the cooling coil started to underperform under the heatwave scenario. The temperature exceeded the cooling setpoint for a longer period than in the previous test, spanning from 11:00 to 21:00.

Figure 6. T_{out}, T_{in}, Q_{A/C} and P_{A/C} with a sizing factor of 1.15 – manual-sized

Figure 7. T_{out}, T_{in}, Q_{A/C} and P_{A/C} without a sizing factor – manual-sized

3.3 Impact of the heatwave on the refrigeration

Figure 8 illustrates the impact of T_{out} and T_{in} on COP_{r,f} and COP_{r,c}. The COP_{r,c} and COP_{r,f} were affected by T_{in}, which is in turn was influenced by T_{out} when the A/C capacity is reached. COP_{r,c} remained stable at 2.70 when T_{in} was constant at 24°C, then dropped, reaching a minimum of 2.26 at 17:00. Similarly, COP_{r,f} remained constant at 1.18 when T_{in} was constant at 24°C, then decreased to a minimum of 1.04 at 17:00.

Figure 8. T_{out}, T_{in}, COP_r and COP_{A/C} without a sizing factor – manual-sized

Figure 9 shows T_{out}, T_{in}, Q_{r,c}, Q_{r,f}, P_{r,c} and P_{r,f}. Between 03:00 and 07:00, there is an increase in Q_{r,c} due to the rise in humidity within the space, caused by the activation of the economiser. While this did have a negative impact on Q_{r,c}, increasing it from 7,955 W to 8,946 W (Figure 9), Q_{A/C} decreased from 3,588 W to 2,058 W (Figure 7). Therefore, the reduction in Q_{A/C} due to the economiser outweighed the increase in Q_{r,c}. For the frozen cabinets, Q_{r,f} and P_{r,f} were lower because they were fewer in number, and had a lower consumption per meter (because they are closed and horizontal) compared to the chilled cabinets. Q_{r,f} increased at 07:00 and declined at 23:00 due to door openings, with slightly higher Q_{r,f} observed during operating hours compared to closing hours. Since Q_{r,f} and P_{r,f} have small values, their lines overlap near zero. This makes the Q_{r,f} line difficult to see.

Figure 9. T_{out}, T_{in}, Q_{r,f}, Q_{r,c}, P_{r,f} and P_{r,c} without a sizing factor – manual-sized

4 CONCLUSIONS

The main objective of this work was to model a typical independent convenience store in the UK and analyse the impact of the summer 2022 heatwave on the store temperature and refrigeration system. Additionally, it aimed to assess the performance of the A/C system under various scenarios. Key findings include:

- During the heatwave, the auto-sized EnergyPlus simulation effectively handled outdoor temperature peaks of 40.15°C, keeping indoor temperatures steady at 24°C, with or without a sizing factor.
- EnergyPlus oversized the cooling capacity, as simulations without a sizing factor and with a maximum temperature of 12.45°C above the design conditions still maintained indoor conditions stable.
- When the A/C system was designed for a maximum temperature of 27.7°C with a 1.15 sizing factor, the store temperature increased by 0.3°C above the setpoint during an extreme heatwave.
- When the A/C system was designed for a maximum temperature of 27.7°C without a sizing factor, the store temperature rose by 4.0°C above the setpoint during an extreme heatwave.

These findings highlight the resilience and limitations of the A/C system in an independent convenience store under extreme heat conditions. If the A/C system was designed using EnergyPlus algorithms, there would be plenty of spare capacity, and the model predicts that the store temperature would remain stable even during the most extreme heatwaves. However, if the A/C is only sufficient to handle the nominal design temperature of 27.7°C, the model predicts the store temperature would increase by 4.0°C.

Although the current system was able to handle high external temperatures with ample spare capacity using EnergyPlus auto-design, the performance issues observed in manually sized cooling coil scenarios indicate that future heatwaves and rising temperatures due to climate change could pose significant challenges to maintaining thermal comfort and refrigeration efficiency if the coil is not oversized. To improve store resilience to future heat events, several adaptation strategies can be considered:

- Improved A/C system design: Implementing higher sizing factors, or warmer design temperatures to cope with extreme heat conditions.
- Adding doors to chilled cabinets: Installing glass doors on open refrigerated display cases can significantly reduce heat gain, lowering refrigeration energy consumption and reducing the cooling load on the A/C system.

It would be expected that non-A/C stores might have even higher internal temperature rises during extreme heat. Therefore, future studies will examine non-A/C stores to assess the impact of extreme weather conditions on store temperatures.

This study only considered the effect on the ambient temperature and refrigeration system in the store. It did not consider the effect on the temperature of the food within the refrigerated cabinets. Therefore, further research should investigate food temperature variations.

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NOMENCLATURE

Abbreviations

A/C	Air Conditioning
ACS	Association of Convenience Stores
ASHRAE	American Society of Heating, Refrigeration and Air conditioning Engineers
CH	Closing Hours
COP	Coefficient Of Performance
DDY	Design Day
DX	Direct Expansion
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
HHA	Heat-Health Alert
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
LT	Low Temperature
MT	Medium Temperature
NREL	National Renewable Energy Laboratory
OH	Opening Hours
PRU	Packaged Rooftop Unit
UK	United Kingdom

Symbols

P	Compressor Electrical Power [W]
Q	Heat Extraction [W]
T	Temperature [°C]

Subscripts

A/C	Air Conditioning
c	Chilled
f	Frozen
in	Indoor
out	Outdoor
r	Refrigeration System
R	Rated
w	Wet-bulb

REFERENCES

ACS, 2018. The Local Shop Report 2018.

ACS, 2021. The Local Shop Report 2021. A report by the Association of Convenience Stores.

ACS, 2024. The Local Shop Report 2024.

BibLus, 2024. Projet d'un supermarché, le guide technique. Accessed in February 2025 from:
<https://biblus.accasoftware.com/fr/comment-concevoir-un-supermarche-le-guide-technique/>.

- Big Ladder Software, 2024. Elements - Weather Data Processing Tool. Retrieved from <https://bigladdersoftware.com/projects/elements>.
- Cabinet Office, 2017. Public Summary of Sector Security and Resilience Plans 2017.
- Danfoss, 2025. CoolSelector2 [Software]. Retrieved February 11, 2025, from <https://www.danfoss.com/en/service-and-support/downloads/dcs/coolselector-2/>.
- DEFRA, 2024. Understanding climate adaptation and the third National Adaptation Programme (NAP3). Retrieved January 2025, from <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/third-national-adaptation-programme-nap3/understanding-climate-adaptation-and-the-third-national-adaptation-programme-nap3#:~:text=Examples%20of%20the%20government's%20approach,planting%20more%20drought%20resistant%20crops>.
- Eid, E., Foster, A., Alvarez, G., Ndoye, F-T., Leducq, D., Evans, J., 2024. Modelling energy consumption in a Paris supermarket to reduce energy use and greenhouse gas emissions using EnergyPlus, International Journal of Refrigeration (2024), doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrefrig.2024.08.023>.
- Franco, A., Cillari, G., & Fantozzi, F., 2021. The potential of building integrated Photovoltaic (BIPV) systems for reducing the energetic impact of Italian supermarkets. E3S Web of Conferences, 31210.1051/e3sconf/202131208020.
- Galvez-Martos, J., Styles, D., & Schoenberger, H., 2013. Identified best environmental management practices to improve the energy performance of the retail trade sector in Europe. Energy Policy, 63, 982. 10.1016/j.enpol.2013.08.061.
- HM Government, 2017. UK Climate Change Risk Assessment 2017.
- IECC, 2012. Accessed in February 2025 from: https://help.iesve.com/ve2021/4_economizers.htm#
- Jones, P., & Comfort, D., 2019. A commentary on the United Kingdom's leading food retailers' resilience plans in the face of climate change. Journal of Public Affairs, 20(2)10.1002/pa.2047.
- Met Office, 2023. Record breaking 2022 indicative of future UK climate. <https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/about-us/news-and-media/media-centre/weather-and-climate-news/2023/record-breaking-2022-indicative-of-future-uk-climate>.
- Met Office, 2025. Climate change in the UK. <https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/>. Retrieved January 2025, from <https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/weather/climate-change/climate-change-in-the-uk>.
- NREL, 2024. DView - EnergyPlus Data Viewer. Retrieved from <https://github.com/NREL/wex/wiki/DView>.
- Schneider, S. H., Semenov, S., Patwardhan, A., Burton, I., Magadza, C. H. D. &, Oppenheimer, M. &, Pittock, A. B., Rahman, A. &, Smith, J. B. &, Suarez, A., & Yamin, F., 2007. Assessing key vulnerabilities and the risk from climate change. Climate Change 2007: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability (pp. 779–810). Cambridge University Press.

- Smeta, 2024. 2.5m Supermarket Open Milk Display Chiller Refrigeration Showcase Open Chiller. Accessed in February 2025 from: <https://smetafacemask.en.made-in-china.com/product/tvdxMwgKyZUB/China-2-5m-Supermarket-Open-Milk-Display-Chiller-Refrigeration-Showcase-Open-Chiller.html>.
- Tassou, S. A., Ge, Y., Hadaway, A., & Marriott, D., 2011. Energy consumption and conservation in food retailing. Applied Thermal Engineering, 31(2-3), 147. 10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2010.08.023.
- UK Parliament, 2019. Committee publish new report on Planetary Health. <https://committees.parliament.uk/>. Retrieved January 2025, from <https://committees.parliament.uk/committee/62/environmental-audit-committee/news/100401/committee-publish-new-report-on-planetary-health/#:~:text=Climate%20change%20and%20other%20stressors,are%20novel%20in%20the%20UK>.
- UNFCCC, 2016. The Paris Agreement. United Nations – Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCC). https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/parisagreement_publication.pdf.
- U.S. Department of Energy, (2024a). EnergyPlus Documentation. Retrieved from <https://energyplus.net>.
- U.S. Department of Energy, (2024b). OpenStudio Documentation. Retrieved from <https://OpenStudio.net>.
- Weatherspark, 2024. July 19, 2022 Weather History at Coningsby Royal Air Force Base. https://weatherspark.com/h/d/147887/2022/7/19/Historical-Weather-on-Tuesday-July-19-2022-at-Coningsby-Royal-Air-Force-Base-United-Kingdom#google_vignette.